

A Pneumatic Feel-Through Wearable Haptic Device

Giulia Pagnanelli^{1,2}, Manuel G. Catalano^{1,2}, and Matteo Bianchi^{1,3}

Abstract—The “Feeling-through” paradigm, which allows simultaneous interaction with physical objects and haptically rendered virtual properties via wearable tactile systems, remains underexplored compared to vision-enabled Augmented Reality. In [1], we introduced the Wearable-Fabric Yielding Display (W-FYD), which uses an elastic thin fabric as the interaction surface with the finger. It allows the delivery of softness-related cues both in active and passive exploration mode, together with sliding stimuli, without blocking the natural cutaneous perception of the user, in teleoperation and AR tasks. However, its size and weight posed limitations. To address this, we developed a miniaturized version, W-FYD AIR, reducing its dimensions from $100 \times 60 \times 36$ mm to $78 \times 45 \times 37$ mm, and its weight, from 100g to 54g, exploiting pneumatically actuated chambers while maintaining the same functionality and performance, as the original one.

I. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, rapid advancements in technology have spurred the development of Wearable Haptic Systems (WHS), which aim to enhance human interaction by artificially replicating the sense of touch through mechanical stimuli such as vibrations, pressure, and other tactile cues [2]. WHS are beneficial because they offer comfortable wear and enhance human-machine interaction (HMI) without significantly hindering natural task execution. However, many WHS use rigid surfaces to provide stimuli, which can interfere with the user’s natural tactile feedback. This makes them unsuitable for tactile Augmented Reality (tAR) as Feel-through wearables. To this aim, recent research has explored the use of functional materials. In [3], we proposed the usage of a fabric-based WHS for the finger, namely the W-FYD [1]. W-FYD relies on a thin elastic fabric (thinner than 1 mm) attached to two DC motors and a lifting mechanism activated via a servomotor. The lifting mechanism allows the fabric to warp the user’s finger, and the DC motors maintain the fabric in a resting stretching state. Based on the force exerted by the user on the object, the lifting height is varied to simulate different contact area growths. By controlling the expansion of the contact area, various perceptions of softness can be achieved. This strategy ultimately determines the contact area spread rate with respect to the indenting force [4], which was proven to be a key element in the human cutaneous perception of softness. Despite its effectiveness in correctly delivering informative tactile cues, its dimensions and weight were identified as limitations. To tackle this issue, we propose a miniaturized version of the system, hereinafter referred to as W-FYD AIR, which allows reducing the overall dimensions of the device from $100 \times 60 \times 36$ mm to $78 \times 45 \times 37$ mm and its

Fig. 1: Comparison between devices: (a) and (b) show the W-FYD and W-FYD AIR, respectively, while (c) and (d) highlight the respective lifting mechanism with the moving components highlighted in red.

weight from 100g to 54g (fig. 1), by exploiting pneumatically-actuated chambers for the lifting mechanism while preserving its tactile feedback capabilities. The work involved several steps: revising the design to miniaturize the structure and embedding the new pneumatic system, developing a new control architecture, characterizing the device, and identifying the system. We demonstrated that the re-designed version of the device kept the same characteristics, with respect to the previous version, in terms of stiffness, workspace, transfer function, and dynamic response. This is promising in the perspective of using the new device in real applications.

II. W-FYD AIR: SYSTEM DESCRIPTION

The W-FYD AIR (fig. 1b) consists of two main components: the base as finger support and the moving frame as actuation systems support. Similar to the previous version, the new device allows for three modes of tactile interaction: a *sliding mode* made by the synchronous movement of the two DC motors that allows the fabric stretching and sliding, an *active mode*, where the user actively probes the interaction surface, and a *passive mode*, where a lifting mechanism brings a fabric in contact with the finger-pad, conveying a tactile cue. The most significant change is the replacement of the servo motor with pneumatic actuation for the lifting mechanism, allowing reducing the overall dimension of our WHS (figs. 1c, 1d). We embedded a soft bag between the base and the moving frame inflated by a remote pump connected to the bag with a small tube that, when inflated, lifts the frame and presses the fabric against the finger. The two DC motors are located on the moving frame with their shaft locked to the frontal aluminum support. Two encoders measure the motor’s angular positions necessary to perform a closed-loop control. Torsional springs are used to ensure stable contact. An elastic fabric is fixed to the motors and wrapped around two pins fixed to the moving frame. As the motors rotate in opposite directions the fabric perform stretching modulation. As the motor rotates synchronously the fabric perform sliding.

¹ Centro di Ricerca “Enrico Piaggio”, Università di Pisa, Largo Lucio Lazzarino 1, 56122 Pisa, Italy; ² Dipartimento di Ingegneria dell’Informazione, Università di Pisa, Largo Lucio Lazzarino 1, 56122 Pisa, Italy; ³ Soft Robotics for Human Cooperation and Rehabilitation, Istituto Italiano di Tecnologia, Via Morego, 30 16163 Genova, Italy giulia.pagnanelli17@gmail.com

This project has received funding in part from the Italian Ministry of University and Research (MUR) - Fondo Italiano per la Scienza (FIS), with the grant PERCEIVING (no. FIS00001153); in part by the European Union by the Next Generation EU project ECS00000017 ‘Ecosistema dell’Innovazione’ Tuscany Health Ecosystem (THE, PNRR, Spoke 9: Robotics and Automation for Health); in part by the Università di Pisa under the ‘PRA – Progetti di Ricerca di Ateneo’ (Institutional Research Grants) under Project PRA_2022.27 ‘ART’.

As the frame moves along the vertical axis, the fabric is pressed against the finger pad. Moreover, the moving frame is equipped with a small contactless infrared (IR) to measure the indentation variation made by the finger movements in the active mode. Two custom-made electronic boards are used to control the overall system whose entire cycle works at a frequency of 200 Hz. The structural parts are made with rapid prototyping technology.

A. Design Components

Hosting the new actuation involved redesigning the moving frame, the base and the clip that host the final part of user's finger (grey elements in fig. 1d), and the cover (green part in fig. 1d). The inflatable bag, was produced by casting the silicone Smooth on Dragon Skin@10 FAST in a mold with a plastic core. For the pump motor and electro-valve, we selected the Conjoin CJP31-C03A1 DC 3V and Conjoin CJV10-C03A1 DC 3V, respectively. We used a Phidgets absolute pressure sensor and characterized it within the [0, 840] mmHg range. We determined the relationship between the sensor's output voltage and actual pressure as $P = 1.9V - 699$, whit P relative pressure in mmHg and V voltage in mV ($R^2 = 0.99$).

B. Control Architecture

To control the W-FYD AIR, we developed two distinct control strategies for fabric stretching and the inflating system, based on the operation modes (active, passive, or sliding). We implemented a control loop for the DC motors and encoders, to regulate fabric stretching and sliding in active and passive modes. By setting the motor angles as $\theta = -\theta_1 = \theta_2$, positive θ stretches the fabric, while negative θ relaxes it. Sliding is controlled by setting $\theta = \theta_1 = \theta_2$. The control strategy for the inflating system, operates in two states: inflates the bag when the valve is closed and the pump is on, and deflates when the valve is open. A closed-loop pressure regulation adjusts the pump's voltage through a PWM signal based on pressure discrepancies (desired-measured). Additionally, the control strategy considers the bag state at the previous step to manage the valve: it remains closed when the reference pressure is constant or increasing and opens only when the reference pressure decreases and the bag pressure exceeds the new reference. This prevents oscillations and overshooting during inflation. Finally, an additional control loop adjusts reference pressure based on frame position measured by an infrared sensor. Tests confirmed that the new soft actuation system efficiently functions as a lifting mechanism, with effective pressure control demonstrated across different fabric stretching states and pressure ranges.

III. SYSTEM CHARACTERIZATION AND IDENTIFICATION

First, we characterized the W-FYD AIR workspace, in terms of force F in N, and indentation δ in mm, following the procedure adopted in [1]. The curves obtained from force-indentation data were opportunely filtered and fitted through a linear interpolation over the different fabric's stretch conditions, resulting in $R^2 > 0.97$. Thus, the force-indentation characteristics can be written as a function of θ as $F = \sigma(\theta)\delta$ ($R^2 = 0.9906$), where $\sigma(\theta)$ is the function that provides the stiffness coefficient for a given value of θ equal to $\sigma(\theta) = ae^{b\theta} = 0.1485e^{0.01334\theta}$. This demonstrates that the W-FYD AIR can reproduce linear stiffness whose associated motor's position θ , can be evaluated as $\theta = \log(\frac{\sigma}{ae^b})$. Additionally, it can replicate non-linear stiffness within its workspace by incorporating the indentation value δ . In active mode, the IR sensor retrieves δ , while in passive mode, it's obtained from

the pump motor's pressure. As commonly used, to describe the stiffness behavior of specimens, we chose the power function $F(\delta) = \lambda\delta^\beta$, with β parametric and λ reproduced by a suitable choice of the motor's position [1]. Considering $\lambda = \frac{F}{\delta^\beta} = \frac{\sigma(\theta)\delta}{\delta^\beta} = \frac{ae^{b\theta}}{\delta^{\beta-1}}$, the motor position can be determined as $\theta = \log(\frac{\lambda\delta^{\beta-1}}{ae^b})$. This demonstrates that the new W-FYD AIR matches the stiffness range of the original W-FYD, between 0.17 and 0.48 N/mm.

The second step involved characterizing the system in terms of pressure (P in mmHg) and displacement (δ in mm). We used a passive marker-based motion tracking system (OptiTrack) to measure displacement due to pressure. Using Matlab/Simulink scheme, we varied bag pressure in 50 mmHg steps from 0 to 200 mmHg, holding each step for four seconds. We first resampled the collected pressure data to ensure consistent measurement frequency and then averaged the data series. We used this average data to fit a linear equation describing the pressure-indentation relationship that resulted best approximated by a linear equation $P(\delta) = 60.06\delta - 34.69$.

The same setup was also used for system identification, aimed to determine the transfer function between pump motor input and device indentation to assess the bandwidth for passive touch interaction. We applied chirp input pressure signals at 100 mmHg, 150 mmHg, and 200 mmHg, each lasting 30 seconds, and measured mobile frame displacement. We tested several polynomial models, finding that the ARX model ($n_a = 1$, $n_b = 1$, $n_k = 1$) offered the best balance of adequacy criterion results and complexity, with a Fit to Estimation Data (FtED) of 95.66% and a Final Prediction Error (FPE) of 2.8014e-04. The Bode diagram analysis showed a low-pass behavior with -3dB and -6dB cut-off frequencies at 2.28 Hz and 3.32 Hz, respectively, consistent with previous W-FYD results [1].

IV. DISCUSSIONS AND CONCLUSIONS

In this work, we presented the miniaturized version of the W-FYD presented in [1] named W-FYD AIR with overall dimension reduced from $100 \times 60 \times 36$ mm to $78 \times 45 \times 37$ mm, and weight from 100g to 54g. We mainly acted on the actuation of the lifting mechanism for the passive exploration mode, substituting the previously used servo motor with pneumatic actuation. Through the characterization and identification processes, we demonstrate that the W-FYD AIR covers the same stiffness range as the original and exhibits similar low-pass behavior with a -3dB cut-off frequency around 3Hz. These results are promising for making the W-FYD AIR suitable for delivering several tactile cues while offering improved comfort and wearability. Future research will involve testing its effectiveness with human participants.

REFERENCES

- [1] S. Fani, S. Ciotti, E. Battaglia, A. Moscatelli, and M. Bianchi, "W-fyd: A wearable fabric-based display for haptic multi-cue delivery and tactile augmented reality," *IEEE Transactions on Haptics*, vol. 11, no. 2, pp. 304–316, 2018.
- [2] C. Pacchierotti, S. Sinclair, M. Solazzi, A. Frisoli, V. Hayward, and D. Prattichizzo, "Wearable haptic systems for the fingertip and the hand: taxonomy, review, and perspectives," *IEEE transactions on haptics*, vol. 10, no. 4, pp. 580–600, 2017.
- [3] S. Fani, S. Ciotti, G. Pagnanelli, A. Moscatelli, Y. De Pra, and M. Bianchi, "Modulating the perceived softness of real objects through wearable haptics," *IEEE Transactions on Haptics*, vol. 16, no. 4, pp. 543–548, 2023.
- [4] A. bicchi, E. Scilingo, and D. De Rossi, "Haptic discrimination of softness in teleoperation: the role of the contact area spread rate," *IEEE Transactions on Robotics and Automation*, vol. 16, no. 5, pp. 496–504, 2000.